

Preliminary Evaluation of Bespoke Spatiotemporal Embeddings for Sub-Pixel Landscape Feature Detection

Luka Antonić^{1*}, Josip Križan¹, Barbara Štimac Tumara¹, Andreja Radović², Ivan Pilaš³

¹ MultiOne Ltd., Zagreb, Croatia, lantonice@multione.hr

² Division for Marine and Environmental Research, Ruđer Bošković Institute, aradovic@irb.hr

³ Division for Forest Ecology, Croatian Forest Research Institute, Jastrebarsko, Croatia, ivanp@sumins.hr

* corresponding author

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.20396350

Abstract: High availability of openly accessible Earth observation (EO) data has unlocked vast potential for low-cost land monitoring. Some monitoring tasks, however, remain challenging to perform using data of 10 metre resolution (currently the best available for open satellite imagery) or lower. This study was performed under the assumption that spatiotemporal raster embeddings hold potential to alleviate the aforementioned difficulties for one specific task: in-pixel detection of landscape features (as defined by the Common Agriculture Policy of the EU) using Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2-based data, as a low-cost alternative to processing high-resolution orthophotographic imagery and on-site surveys. Evaluation of this principal assumption was performed by using spatiotemporal embeddings of Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2-derived datasets (produced by a naive CNN autoencoder) as covariates for pixel-based classification. Preliminary evaluation demonstrated potential applicability of the method, with F1 scores above 0.8 for over half of the evaluated landscape feature classes on the validation dataset.

Keywords: spatiotemporal raster embeddings; landscape feature detection.

1 Introduction

Due to the available spatial resolution of openly accessible Earth observation (EO) data (10x10 metre pixel size and above), sub-pixel object detection is necessary to complete many types of land monitoring tasks without the use of commercial satellite imagery or airborne surveys (which increase monitoring costs significantly). One such task was performed as part of an ESA-PECS activity from 2024 to 2025: detection of landscape feature, as defined by the Common Agricultural Policy of the EU (European Commission 2023), instances on agricultural land. A key method for enhancing landscape feature detectability within 10 metre covariate pixels was enhancing the covariate space with spatiotemporal embeddings, which were then included as raster covariates in the downstream object detection method (treated as a multiclass classification task, with per-pixel landscape feature presence probability rasters as the primary output). While significant advancements in geospatial embedding models were achieved relatively recently (Feng et al. 2025, Brown et al. 2025, Tseng et al. 2023), these are largely global, foundational models, which require either massive EO datasets to train, or alternatively lock the downstream consumer of pre-inferred embeddings into fixed thematic resolution. An alternative approach was evaluated within

this study: generation of bespoke embeddings, where the embedding model (a simple 3D convolutional autoencoder) was trained over a narrow spatial scope (though still larger than the number of pixels containing ground truth data for the downstream detection task), but on hand-picked EO datasets, namely Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 imagery, along with a phenological indicator raster product. The overall goal of this approach was to introduce relevant spatiotemporal context in and around the pixel as a covariate set, while preserving the downstream modelling method (and more importantly, its requirements for target dataset size), and while still keeping the autoencoder training dataset narrow enough to represent only the area of interest for landscape feature detection. Application of the method resulted in uniformly improved generalisation of the downstream model: the model performed with an F1-score above 0.8 for four out of seven landscape feature classes, compared to achieving such performance only for one class when the downstream task was performed without embedding covariates.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Ground truth and covariate datasets

As the foremost (albeit incomplete) public repository of agricultural land data for Croatia, the national land parcel identification system - ARKOD (Agency for Payments in Agriculture and APPRRR 2022) dataset was used as the sole source of ground truth for landscape feature presence. ARKOD identifies and contains positional (vector) data for 7 landscape feature classes: ditch, drywall, grove, hedge, pond, single tree and tree line. The full, nation-wide spatial extent of the dataset was used in this study, with only the inventory for the year 2022 taken into account. Target labels for classification were produced as binary masks through rasterisation of the landscape feature data into a 10 metre resolution grid (in the ETRS89-extended / LAEA Europe coordinate reference system). An additional class (other), representing absence of any of the aforementioned landscape features, was produced as a binary mask of negative 10 metre buffers around all ARKOD parcels with confirmed presence of landscape features, with the exclusion of pixels with registered landscape features. A sample of the label mask for drywall is shown in Figure 1. Mixed pixels (those containing more than one landscape feature class) were removed from the final ground truth dataset. Three covariate datasets (with coverage spanning the full land territory of Croatia and the year 2022) were used: 1) Sentinel-2 imagery (blue, green,

Figure 1. ARKOD-derived label mask sample with 10m pixels confirmed to contain drywall shown in red, basemap provided by (State Geodetic Administration of the Republic of Croatia (DGU) 2023).

Figure 2. Samples of covariate datasets: Sentinel-2 NIR band seasonal median for summer 2022 (left), Sentinel-1 GRD VH monthly mean for April 2022 (center), PPI seasonal trajectory for 1st of April 2022 (right) rendered to emphasise local variability, with color ranging from P02 (red) to P98 (blue), basemap provided by (State Geodetic Administration of the Republic of Croatia (DGU) 2023).

Figure 3. Samples of embedding rasters (band 1 of 64): Sentinel-2 NIR P50 (left), Sentinel-1 GRD VH (center), PPI seasonal trajectories (right) rendered to emphasise local variability, with color ranging from P02 (red) to P98 (blue), basemap provided by (State Geodetic Administration of the Republic of Croatia (DGU) 2023).

red and NIR bands) (Copernicus 2022b), 2) Sentinel-1 GRD imagery (VV and VH polarisation) (Copernicus 2022a) and 3) Copernicus Plant Phenology Index (10 metre, 10-day seasonal trajectories) (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service 2022). Sentinel-2 imagery was aggregated into annual and seasonal mosaics (P25 and P50) via the mosaicking method described in (Witjes et al. 2023), while Sentinel-1 imagery was aggregated into per-pixel monthly mean values. All three covariate datasets were resampled into a common 10 metre grid, identical to that of the ground truth label masks. Samples of the covariate datasets are shown in Figure 2.

2.2 Embedding generation

A simple 3D convolutional autoencoder was trained for each of the following covariate timeseries: 1) seasonal Sentinel-2 mosaics (one timeseries per each combination of band and percentile), 2) monthly Sentinel-1 mosaics (one timeseries per polarisation) and 3) 10-day PPI product (one timeseries), on 5x5 windows surrounding each pixel within the full ground truth mask. The autoencoder was implemented using PyTorch (Ansel et al. 2024), with two Conv3d and ConvTranspose3d layers at the encoder and decoder halves, respectively, and a single 64-sized fully connected layer at the end of the encoder half. ReLU activation was used, as well as layer normalisation and 50% dropout rate. By performing inference with the encoder portion of the trained model, spatiotemporal context was encoded as rasters containing per-pixel 64-sized embedding vectors. The resulting embedding rasters were used as additional covariates for in-pixel landscape feature detection. Embedding raster samples are shown in Figure 3.

2.3 Classification

The in-pixel object detector was implemented as a multiclass XGBoost (Chen and Guestrin 2016) classifier, with hyperparameters (learning rate, depth and subsampling - the number of estimators was left to be determined through 5-round early stopping) tuned for optimal weighted F1 score, via random parameter search (100 iterations) under 2-fold cross-validation. Two separate classifiers were trained with and without embedding covariates to estimate the effect of the additional context provided by embeddings. In order to mitigate some of the class imbalance between landscape feature classes, the training dataset was limited to a maximum of 100 000 samples per class, 20% of which were held out from training and used as validation samples. Classifier predictions were produced as per-class, per-pixel probability rasters over an agricultural land mask obtained through combining ARKOD parcel geometry with the geometry of two Corine Land Cover (European Environment Agency (EEA) 2018) agricultural classes: non-irrigated arable land (211) and permanently irrigated land (212).

3 Results

Classification metrics against the validation dataset without and with the use of embedding covariates are shown in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. While the classifier achieved near-perfect scores when evaluated against the training dataset in both cases (below 0.5% error rates), evaluation against the validation dataset has shown noticeable, albeit not dramatic, improvement through the use of embedding covariates. The confusion matrix resulting from the inclusion of embedding covariates (including indication of performance increment compared to the baseline case) is shown in Figure 4. While classification metrics within the bounds of the training and validation dataset suggested useful performance, inference across the wider agricultural land mask revealed disproportionate predictions of landscape feature distribution even for high-performing classes, as shown for drywall in Figure 5.

Table 1. Classification metrics against validation dataset without embedding covariates.

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
ditch	0.76	0.79	0.77	13197
drywall	0.83	0.92	0.87	18456
grove	0.74	0.85	0.79	18066
hedge	0.71	0.79	0.75	15932
pond	0.95	0.38	0.54	380
single tree	0.49	0.13	0.20	3957
tree line	0.75	0.53	0.62	7634
other	0.80	0.74	0.77	19851
accuracy			0.77	97473
macro avg	0.75	0.64	0.66	97473
weighted avg	0.76	0.77	0.75	97473

Table 2. Classification metrics against validation dataset with embedding vectors included as covariates.

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
ditch	0.81	0.85	0.83	13197
drywall	0.85	0.93	0.89	18456
grove	0.84	0.92	0.88	18066
hedge	0.79	0.88	0.83	15932
pond	1.00	0.55	0.71	380
single tree	0.65	0.18	0.28	3957
tree line	0.87	0.72	0.79	7634
other	0.84	0.77	0.81	19851
accuracy			0.83	97473
macro avg	0.83	0.72	0.75	97473
weighted avg	0.83	0.83	0.82	97473

Figure 4. Confusion matrix against validation dataset with the use of embedding covariates, with difference in absolute number of pixels (compared to the case without embedding covariates) per true-predicted pair shown in square brackets, where applicable, the colormap represents the ratio of the number of pixels per true-predicted pair to the total sample size per class.

Figure 5. Sample of inferred probability map for in-pixel presence of drywall: disproportionately high probability of drywall presence (well above 50%) even in pixels which observably do not contain instances of drywall.

4 Discussion

Model performance against the validation dataset suggests detectability of the seven landscape feature classes within 10 metre pixels. While both models behaving almost as perfect classifiers against the training dataset indicates some degree of overfitting (which can be attributed to the hyperparameter tuning method - tuning learning rate while allowing the gradient booster to apply a large number of additional estimators as long as early stopping allows it), the noticeable increase in classification metrics against the validation dataset shows that generalisation capability has increased with the addition of spatiotemporal context in the form of autoencoder-extracted embeddings. This is especially evident when it is taken into account that performance has increased uniformly for all landscape

feature classes, while relative performance between different classes remained similar. Considering also that the described embedding generation method is indeed suboptimal, most notably when compared to recent advances in EO embedding foundational models like (Feng et al. 2025, Brown et al. 2025, Tseng et al. 2023), it can be expected that there is significant potential in the use of embeddings for sub-pixel object detection.

5 Conclusion

The results of this study strongly imply that bespoke spatiotemporal embeddings have significant potential to improve model generalisation for in-pixel object detection tasks, even when generated using a naively constructed 3D convolutional autoencoder. Further work towards investigating the described method should firstly include

benchmarking it against in-pixel object detection modelling on readily available global embedding datasets generated with state-of-the-art foundational models, and secondly, utilise advances in foundational models to improve bespoke embedding generation, either through transfer learning or atomic architectural improvements to the embedding model.

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